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“STUDY OF DRUG-DRUG INTERACTIONS IN INPATIENTS ADMITTED TO DEPARTMENT OF GENERAL MEDICINE AT A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL, BALLARI KARNATAKA”

Dr. RoopaShree P.M*, Dhruba Rana Chhetri, Varun Lal, Sujit Kumar Sah, Sahithi Reddy D, Kotha Ashok Guptha

Department of Pharmacy Practice, TVM College of Pharmacy, Ballari, Karnataka.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Drug can be useful tools in the prevention and treatment of symptoms and diseases, but if not use properly, they may be harmful and cause new symptoms. Clinically significant drug interactions can occur when two or more drugs are taken in combination. Objectives: To study potential Drug -Drug interactions in inpatients medication charts in general medicine department of a tertiary care teaching hospital in Ballari. Methodology: The study period was 6 months. Data of all the subjects prescribed with more than two drugs. Results and Discussion: A total of 220 prescriptions were analyzed of which 150(68.18%) cases were identified with DDIs and 70(31.82%) were without DDIs .Among 150 patients 124(56.36%) were males and 96(43.64%) were females. In correlation higher prevalence rate of DDI among males (62.70%).Out of 150 cases a majority of DDI were found frequently in the age group of 59-68(20.667%). A total of 676 DDIs were obtained from 150 cases. From these 97(14.35%) were of Major severity, 434(64.20%) were of moderate severity and 145(21.45%) of minor severity. Drugs with potential DDIs identified, followed by anti-platelets (n=154), Anti-diabetic (n=110). Among 150 cases Pharmacokinetic outcome was identified in 172 DDIs, Pharmacodynamics outcome was indentified in 435 DDIs and 69 were Non specified interactions. Among 150 patients there were 55(25%) with Cardiovascular diseases,53(24.09%) with Renal disorders,32(14.55%) with Respiratory disorder, 22(10%) with Central nerves system disorder, 21(9.55%) with Endocrinal disorder, 16(7.27%) with GI, 10(4.59%)with Blood disorder, 7(3.18%) with Hepatic disorder, 20(0.9%) with Immune system disorders and 2(0.9%) were Others.

Corresponding author

Dr. RoopaShree P.M

Y. Nagesha Shastry Nagar,
Kappagal Road Ballari Dist.,
Karnataka-583103
Dr. Roopashree P.M,
+919916200670
drroopa.pmath@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Drug can be useful tools in the prevention and treatment of symptoms and diseases, but if not use properly, they may be harmful and cause new symptoms (or) produce suboptimal effect. Clinically significant drug interactions can occur when two or more drugs are taken in combination. Clinical management of drug-drug interactions should includes monitoring of a patient's therapy and making appropriate adjustments in the drug regimen can reduce potentially significant drug interactions.¹

Drug – drug interactions (DDIs) are defined as drug combinations resulting in a pharmacological or clinical response, which differs from response to the agents when either is given alone.²

A potential drug interaction is a situation in which one drug affects the activity of another drug, when both are administered together. It may result in increased or decreased effects of the drugs or a new effect can be produced that neither produces on its own. The drug-drug interaction increases as the number of medications increase.³

Drug-drug interaction (DDIs) in patients receiving multi-drug therapy is of wide concern.²

Drug-Drug Interactions (DDI) can results from minor morbidities up to fatal consequences.⁴

It is believed that the potential for drug-drug interaction reaches 100% when the number of drugs prescribed reaches eight.⁷

In every potential drug-drug interaction, an index drug and an interacting drug is involved. The drug for which the pharmacological or clinical response is altered is called the index drug, and the drug that induces the interaction is the interacting drug.¹⁴

Based on the profile of medications prescribed, the drug-drug interactions are identified and classified.

1. According to severity, potential Drug -Drug Interaction (DDIs) are classified as:

- Major: The effects are potentially life threatening or capable of causing permanent damage. Ex: Aspirin- Clopidogrel: Concurrent use may result in increased risk of bleeding.
- Moderate: The effects may cause deterioration in patients' clinical status and additional treatment or extension of hospital stay. Ex : Atorvastatin- Phenytoin : Concurrent use may result in decreased atorvastatin plasma concentration
- Minor: The effects are usually mild. Consequences may be bothersome or unnoticeable but should not significantly affect the therapeutic outcome Ex: Ranitidine- Theophylline: Concurrent use may result in theophylline toxicity.

2. According to the mechanism, pDDIs were classified as:

- Pharmacokinetic:-
- Pharmacodynamic
- Pharmacokinetic+ Pharmacodynamic

3. Pharmacokinetic pDDIs were further classified as either increase/decrease in:

- Absorption
- Distribution
- Metabolism
- Excretion.

4. Pharmacodynamic pDDIs were further classified as:

- Synergistic
- Antagonistic.²⁹

Pharmacodynamic interactions are those where the effects of one drug are changed by the presence of another drug at its site of action.⁸

The examples for most dangerous drug combinations include warfarin interactions NSAIDs, sulfonamides, macrolides, or quinolones; angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor interactions with potassium supplements or spironolactone; digoxin interactions with amiodarone; and theophylline interactions with quinolones.²¹ The main objective of this study is to analyze drug-drug interactions in medication chart of the patients admitted in General medicine unit of a tertiary care teaching hospital.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study involves the collection of data prospectively from the Medicine Department of a Vijayanagara institute of medical sciences tertiary care teaching hospital, Ballari, Karnataka. The study was conducted for a period of six months. 220 patient's treatment chart were collected according to Inclusion and Exclusion criteria and studied Patient's demographic details, medication history, therapeutic category were collected and was documented in a suitably designed data collection form. drug interactions was assessed by using Lexicomp.

Study Criteria:

A) Inclusion criteria: Patients above 18 years of age.

- Patients of either sex.
- Patients prescribed with minimum of two or more drugs.

B) Exclusion criteria:

- Pregnant and lactating women.
- Patients who are not willing to participate in the study.

RESULTS**Table 01: Distribution of Prescription According to Gender.**

S.N.	GENDER	NO. OF PATIENTS	% OF PATIENTS
1.	Male	124	56.36%
2.	Female	96	43.64%

Figure 01: Distribution of Prescription According to Gender.**Table 02: Distribution of Cases According to Age Group (n=150).**

S.No.	AGE GROUPS	NO. OF CASES	% OF CASES
1.	18-28 Yrs	24	16%
2.	29-38 Yrs	23	15.333%
3.	39-48 Yrs	28	18.667%
4.	49-58 Yrs	26	17.333%
5.	59-68 Yrs	31	20.667%
6.	>68 Yrs	18	12%
	TOTAL	150	100%

Figure 02: Distribution of Cases According to Age Group.**Table 03: Distribution of cases with respective with DDIs.**

S. No.	TYPE OF CASES	NO. OF CASES	% OF CASES
1.	No. of cases with DDI	150	68.18 %
2.	No. of cases without DDI	70	31.82 %
3.	Total no. of cases	220	100%

Disturbation of Cases with respective with DDIs

Figure 03: Distribution of Cases with Respective with DDIs.

Table 04: Classification of DDIs According to Severity (N = 676).

S. N.	TYPE OF INTERACTION	NO. INTERACTION	% OF INTERACTION
1.	Major	97	14.349 %
2.	Moderate	434	64.201%
3.	Minor	145	21.450 %
4.	Total	676	100%

Classification of DDIs According to Severity

Figure 04: Classification of DDIs According to Severity (N = 676).

Table 05: Number of DDIs in Gender Wise.

S.N.	GENDER	MAJOR	MODERATE	MINOR	TOTAL
1.	Male	48 (12.31%)	252 (64.63%)	90 (23.08%)	390 (100%)
2.	Female	49 (17.13%)	182 (63.64%)	55 (19.23%)	286 (100%)

Number of DDIs in Gender Wise

Figure 05: Number of DDIs in Gender Wise.

Table 06: Most Prevalence Class of Drug Involved in DDIs.

S.N.	DRUG CLASSIFICATION	NO. FREQUENCY INVOLVED IN DDIs
1.	Diuretics	170 (12.57%)
2.	Antiplatelet	154 (11.39%)
3.	Antidiabetic	110 (8.13%)
4.	Antiemetic	98 (7.24%)
5.	Antacids	95 (7.02%)
6.	Iron salts	80 (5.91%)
7.	Flouroquinolones	70 (5.17%)
8.	Antiepileptic	69 (5.10%)
9.	Hypolipidaemic	54 (3.99%)
10.	CCB	46 (3.40%)
11.	Beta-blocker	37 (2.73%)
12.	Vasodilator	33 (2.44%)
13.	Macrolide antibiotic	31 (2.29%)
14.	PPI	30 (2.21%)
15.	Corticosteroid	25 (1.84%)

Figure 06: Most Prevalance Class of Drug Involved in DDIs.

Table 07: Mechanism of DDIs.

MECHANISM	NUMBER OF DDIs	PERCENTAGE
PHARMACOKINETIC	172	24%
PHARMACODYNAMIC	435	67%
NON-SPECIFIC	69	9%

Figure 7: Mechanism of DDIs.

Table 08: DDIs based on Organ system.

S.N.	ORGAN SYSTEM	NO. OF ORGAN SYTEM INVOLVED	Percentage (%)
1.	Cardio Vascular System	55	25%
2.	Renal system	53	24.09%
3.	Respiratory system	32	14.55%
4.	Central Nervous System	22	10%
5.	Endocrine system	21	9.55%
6.	Gastro Intestinal System	16	7.27%
7.	Blood Disorder	10	4.59%
8.	Hepatic system	7	3.18%
9.	Immune System (IDV)	2	0.90%
10.	Others	2	0.90%

Figure 08: DDI Based on Organ System.

Table 09: Distribution of DDI in Different Age Group.

S.N.	AGE	MAJOR DDI	MODERATE DDI	MINOR DDI	TOTAL	% OF DDI
1.	18-28	22	44	23	89	13.166 %
2.	29-38	23	55	13	92	13.609 %
3.	39-48	11	86	30	127	18.787 %
4.	49-58	9	89	28	126	18.639 %
5.	59-68	20	112	39	171	25.296 %
6.	>69	12	48	11	71	10.503 %

Figure 09: Distribution of DDI in Different Age Group.

Table10 : Gender wise categorization of subjects enrolled with or without DDIs.

S.N.	GENDER	PATIENT WITH DDI	PATIENT WITHOUT DDI	TOTAL
1.	Male	88 (70.97%)	36 (29.03%)	124
2.	Female	62 (64.58%)	34 (35.45%)	96
	TOTAL	150 (68.18%)	70 (31.82%)	220

Figure 10: Gender Wise Categorization of subjects Enrolled With or Without DDIs.**Table 11: Number of Interaction Per Patient.**

S.No.	NUMBER OF INTERACTION	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	% OF PATIENTS
1.	1 Interaction	24	16%
2.	2 Interactions	17	11.33%
3.	3 Interactions	28	18.66%
4.	4 Interactions	20	13.33%
5.	5 Interactions	14	9.33%
6.	6 Interactions	12	8%
7.	7 Interactions	8	5.33%
8.	8 Interactions	7	4.66%
9.	9 Interactions	6	4%
10.	10 Interactions	2	1.33%
11.	11 Interactions	2	1.33%
12.	12 Interactions	2	1.33%
13.	13 Interactions	3	2%
14.	14 Interactions	2	1.33%
15.	>14 Interactions	3	2%

Figure 11: Number of Interaction Per Patient.

Table No. 12 : Most Prevalent Drug-Drug Interaction.

S.No.	Drug combination	Severity	Consequences of DDI
1	Ciprofloxacin+ondansetron	Major	Moderate Risk QTc-Prolonging Agents may enhance the QTc-prolonging effect of other Moderate Risk QTc-Prolonging Agents
2	Aspirin +Clpidogrel	Moderate	Agents with Antiplatelet Properties may enhance the antiplatelet effect of other Agents with Antiplatelet Properties.
3	Aspirin +Calcium Carbonate	Minor	Antacids may decrease the serum concentration of Salicylates.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, the prevalence of Drug-Drug Interactions was evaluated Vijayanagara institute of medical sciences in a tertiary care teaching hospital Ballari, Karnataka and it was found to be 68.18 %. In correlation, a study conducted by Biradar s.m, et al showed that prevalence of Drug-Drug Interaction was 69.33%.¹⁶ In the present study, A total of 220 prescriptions were analyzed during the study period out of which 124(56.36%) were males and 96(43.64%) were females. In correlation higher prevalence rate of DDI among males (62.70%) was reported by Trushar Umretiya et.al⁶. In our study, the prevalence of DDI was prevalent among the people of 59-68 age group (20.68%), These results are in line with other studies which also showed that DDIs are more frequent in older patients who are on polypharmacy.¹⁸ In this study the collected data was analysed for DDIs by using commercially available software LEXICOMP. Out of 220 cases, 150(68.18%) cases were identified with DDIs and 70(31.82%) were without DDIs. Similar results were found in the study conducted by Trushar Umretiya et.al the prevalence of DDIs was 63%.⁶ In our present study the total number of interactions were 676 out of which the interactions in male patients major DDIs were 48, Moderate were 252 and 90 were minor interactions whereas in female patients major ,moderate and minor were 49, 182 & 55. These results were similar to results obtained by Biradar S.M et al.¹⁶

In our study The identified DDIs were analyzed as Major, Moderate & Minor. A total of 676 DDIs were obtained from 150 cases. From these 97(14.35%) were of Major severity, 434(64.20%) were of moderate severity and 145(21.45%) of Minor severity. A majority of identified DDIs were of moderate severity. It was evident from the studies conducted by Ali Qureshi et.al the results were Major (9.58%), moderate (58.53%) and minor (32.87%).²⁵ In our study the prevalence of class of drugs was Diuretics(12.57%), followed by Antiplatelets(11.39%), Antidiabetic(8.13%). The most frequent class of medications implicated in DDI were Diuretics, were found highly intractable substances where as corticosteroids were less intractable. The results of our study correlates with the study conducted by Biradar S.M et al in which the diuretics(15.14%), antidiabetic (5.04%), PPI(8.25%).¹⁶ These findings were different from another study reported in the literature were the medications of inpatient were of concern and pharmacodynamic DDI were dominant¹⁵. In our study Among 150 patients there were 55(25%) diagnosed with cardiovascular diseases, 53(24.09%) diagnosed with renal disorder. The large numbers of active substance prescribed with major DDIs related to the CVS which is similar to the findings described in studies carried out in setting.¹² A higher frequency of prescription drugs acting on CVS is expected among adults and elderly individuals. The second class of drugs most involved with major DDI were those acting on the renal system which is consistent with findings described in a previous study.¹⁵

In our study among 150 prescriptions containing DDIs the distribution of age groups of DDIs showed that the age group of 59-68 had the maximum number of DDIs(25.29%), The finding in this study are in agreement with the results obtained in the study conducted by Jorge Juarez Vieira Teixeira,et.al the result obtained was in the mean age of 61 years.¹² In our study Among 220 patients, 88(70.97%) male patients were with DDIs and 62(64.58%) were females and 70 (31.82%) patients did not show any DDIs. This result were similar to the study conducted by Biradar S.M. et.al (2016) in which among 104 DDIs ,59 were observed with males and 45 were in females, 46 did to show any DDIs.¹⁶ In the present study a total number of 150 patients had DDIs, Among them 24 (16%) patients were only with one DDI followed by 17 (11.33%) patients with two interactions and others were with more than two interactions. The results of our study were less than the one conducted by Trushar Umretiya et al in which patients with one DDI were (22.79%), followed by (14.28%) had two DDIs.⁶

CONCLUSION

The prospective study was carried out to analyze Drug-Drug interactions in medication chart of the patients admitted in general medicine unit of a tertiary care teaching hospital Vijayanagara institute of medical sciences, Ballari, Karnataka.

A total number of 220 prescriptions were taken up and required information was collected by using standard proforma. The collected information was analyzed. This study was concluded as follows. Male patients were 124(56.36%) and Female patients were 96(43.64%). The number of patient's between the ages 59-68 years 172(25.25%) were more. Out of 220 prescription, 150(68.18%) of prescription containing Drug-Drug interactions. Moderate drug interactions were found in 434(64.20%), Severe were 97(14.35%) and minor were 145(21.45%). Major Number of prescriptions with Drug interactions was found in Cardiovascular system 55(25%). Our study concludes that the incidence rate of DDIs is high at the study site. Majority of the patients were on polypharmacy. The identified predictors responsible for DDIs were polypharmacy, age, sex, duration of hospital stay. The incidence rate of DDIs was high in the patients treated for cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. Hence, it is important to develop a systemic approach to minimize possible DDIs. The clinicians at the study site require educational programs in regard of identification and management of DDIs. Health care professionals should be aware of the risks and should cut down unnecessary medications to prevent the poly pharmacy from occurring. This study can be recommended for carry out similar study, which may assure the patient safety and enhanced patient quality of life by means of identifying and possibly preventing them.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Author declares no conflict of interest.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

S.No.	ABBREVIATION	EXPANSION
1	DDIs	Drug – Drug Interactions
2	ADRs	Adverse Drug Reactions
3	ADEs	Adverse Drug Events
4	MP	Medical Practitioner
5	GP	General Practitioner
6	WHO	World Health Organisation
7	CCB	Calcium Channel Blockers
8	PPI	Proton Pump Inhibitors
9	ICU	Intensive Care Unit

REFERENCES

1. Jimmy O.D et al., carried out a study on Drug-drug Interactions in the Medication Charts in Medicine reference Department at Martha's Hospital, Bangalore. Indian Journal of Pharmacy Practice Volume 5 Issue 4 Oct - Dec, 2012.
2. Mahendra Kumar Bj et al., carried out a Prospective study on Incidence and pattern of potential drug interactions of antimicrobial agents in the department of medicine in a tertiary care teaching hospital at Srii Adichunchanagiri Hospital and Research Centre,B.G Nagar. Asian J Pharm Clin Res, Vol 4, Suppl 2, , 31-36, 2011.
3. Kaliasurthy K. et al., carried out a study on drug-drug interactions in inpatients of general medicine department in a tertiary care teaching hospital at sri Ramachandra Medical Centre,Chennai.
4. Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science Vol. 5 (12), pp. 122-124, December, 2015.
5. Mukhopadhyay T, et al., carried out a study on study on polypharmacy can cause drug- drug interactions and its severity analysis among patients admitted in general medicine & CCU of a tertiary care teaching hospital in Eastern India . World journal of pharmaceutical research ,6(2)1412-1420 , January-February, 2017.
6. Chelkeba L et al.,Conducted a study on Assessment of potential drug-drug interactions among outpatients receiving cardiovascular medications at Jimma University specialized hospital, South West Ethiopia.
7. International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology , Vol 2, Issue 2, March-April 2013.
8. Umretiya T,et al., conducted a study on Assessment of Potential Drug-Drug Interactions in the Department of Medicine at Basaweshwara Teaching and General Hospital,Gulbarga. RGUHS J Pharm Sci, Vol 5, Issue 3, Jul-Sep, 2015.
9. Amirthalingam S. et al.,Conducted a study on Analysis of In- Patients Drug Interaction at S.K Hospital,Gujarath. Der Pharmacia Lettre, 2 (1) 368-373, 2010.
10. Bollu M, et al., carried out a study onA Prospective study on Drug – Drug Interactions in the medication charts in general medicine wards, in a tertiary care hospital , Guntur , AP. International Journal of Biological & Pharmaceutical Research.; 5(4): 374-377. 2014
11. TahirSiddiqui M, et al., carried out a study on Assessment of the prevalence of drug–drug interactions in the medical intensive care unit of a tertiary care teaching hospital in India. Mohd.TahirSiddiqui et al. Ijppr.Human, Vol. 4 (3): 102-112, October 2015.
12. Barot P.A, et al., carried out a study on Evaluation of Potential Drug-Drug Interactions in Patients of Emergency Medicine Department at a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital. International Journal of Scientific Study , ,Vol 3 , Issue 5, August 2015.
13. Gupta M, et al., carried out a study on Potential drug-drug interactions among critically ill patients at a tertiary care hospital . International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology , Vol 5 , Issue 4 , July-August 2016 .
14. Teixeira J.J.V, et al., carried out a study on Potential Drug-Drug Interactions in Prescriptions to Patients over 45 Years of Age in Primary Care, Southern Brazil. PLOS ONE , Volume 7 , Issue 10 , e47062 , October 2012.
15. Abideen S, et al., carried out a study on Assesment of prevalence of potential drug-drug interactions in medical intensive care unit of a tertiary care hospital in India. Asian J Pharm Clin Res, Vol 8, Issue 1, 125-130 , 2015.
16. Arvind Nag K, et al., carried out a study on Assessment of drug-drug interactions in hospitalized patients in India. Asian J Pharm Clin Res, Vol 4, Suppl 1, 62-65 , 2011.
17. Kulkarni V, et al., carried out a study on Drug–drug interactions through prescription analysis in a south Indian teaching hospital. Therapeutic Advances in Drug Safety 4(4) 141–146 , 2013.
18. S. M. Biradar, et al., carried out a study on Assessment of potential drug-drug interactions in in-patients of a medicine ward of a tertiary care hospital. Biradar et al. Int. J. Res. Biosciences, 5(1), 76-82, December 2016.
19. Soherwardi s, et al., carried out a study on Surveillance of the potential drug-drug interactions in the medicine department of a tertiary care hospital. Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research. (Suppl), Vol-6(7): 1258-1261, September 2012.
20. Ahmad A, et al., carried out a study on Evaluation of potential drug - drug interactions in general medicine ward of teaching hospital in Southern India. Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research. Vol-9(2): FC10-FC13 Feb 2015.
21. D.M. Oliveir D, et al., carried out a study on Potential drug-drug interactions in a Brazilian teaching hospital. Rev Ciênc Farm Básica Apl.36(3):435-444,2015.
22. Kapadia J, et al., carried out study on a study of Potential drug-drug interactions in indoor patients of medicine department at a tertiary care hospital. Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science Vol. 3 (10), pp. 089-096, October, 2013.
23. A. Dopour, et al., carried out a study on Prospective study on identification and assessment of potential drug-drug interactions in emergency medicine department at KIMS hospital and research centre.
24. International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Science, 6(1) ; 36 – 39 , March 2016.
25. Siby L, et al., carried out a study on Detection of potential drug-drug interactions in prescriptions dispensed in hospital pharmacy. International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences; 7(4): (P) 54 - 59, October 2016 .
26. M Safdar, et al., carried out a study of Drug-Drug interaction in medicine department of a tertiary care teaching hospital. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, Pg 6114-6118, July 2016.
27. Jimmy O.D, et al., carried out study to identify and analyse potential drug- drug interactions from the medication charts of medicine units of a tertiary care teaching hospital, Davangere. International Journal for Pharmaceutical Research Scholars (IJPRS) V-4, I-1, ISSN No: 2277 - 7873, March 2015.
28. Qureshi A, et al., carried out a study on Drug-Drug interactions (DDIs); Prevalence of various levels in prescriptions at public sector teaching hospital of Hyderabad, Pakistan. Professional Med J;24(2):239-243, December 2016.
29. Lubinga SJ, et al., carried out a study on Potential drug-drug interactions on in-patient medication prescriptions at Mbarara regional referral hospital (MRRH) in western Uganda: prevalence, clinical importance and associated factors. African Health Sciences Vol 11 No 3 September 2011.

30. Chavdal N.B, et al., carried out a study of potential drug–drug interaction between prescribed drugs in patients attending outpatient department of medicine at tertiary-care hospital in south Gujarat region. National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology , Vol 5 , Issue 3,September 2015.
31. Pankti S. Patel P.S, et al., carried out a study of potential adverse drug -drug interactions among prescribed drugs in medicine outpatient department of a tertiary care teaching hospital. Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacy Vol. 5 , Issue 2 , March-May 2014
32. Ben D Synder , Thomas M Polasek , Mattew P Doogue . Drug interactions: Principles and practice . Australian Prescriber . june 2012: 35(3).
33. Akshaya Srikanth Bhagavathula, Alemayehu Berhanie, Habtamu Tigistu, Yishak Abraham, Yosheph Getachew, Tahir Mehmood Khan, Chandrashekhar Unakal. Prevalence of Potential Drug-Drug Interactions among internal Medicine ward in University of Gondar Teaching Hospital, Ethiopia. Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine 2014; 4 (1).

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